

Using Large Language Models for the Recommendation of Vegan-Friendly Restaurant Menus

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Received: Jul 1, 2025

Accepted: Aug 1, 2025

Published: Aug 5, 2025

Abstract: This paper investigates the potential of large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT-4 and Gemini 1.5, to enhance the vegan dining experience in Switzerland by analyzing unstructured restaurant menu data to give users accurate recommendations for vegan options. With the main research question: “How can large language models efficiently be used to identify suitable vegan restaurants?” The study evaluates the ability of the two different LLMs to accurately classify vegan dishes, out of PDF menu data and how well users perceive the recommendation abilities of each of them. Creating an experimental setup and including a user test with a survey, we found that ChatGPT-4 demonstrated superior performance compared to Gemini 1.5 in accuracy, relevance, and user satisfaction, although both models struggled with icon-based labeling, multilingual datasets, unstructured menu formats and overall identifying all vegan menu options correctly. Structured prompt engineering improved the differentiation between vegan and vegetarian options and could reduce wrong results, although it was limited in its possibilities to increase the number of reconciled vegan menu options compared to no structured prompt engineering.

Key words: Larger language models; LLMs; ChatGPT-4; ChatGPT-4; recommender systems; restaurant recommendations; evaluation

1. Introduction

Finding a suitable restaurant for a vegan is usually a bit more difficult than restaurants with vegetarian or meat options. There are travel recommender applications such as Tripadvisor (2024) where it is possible to filter for vegan options, but this sometimes just includes a salad and therefore does not satisfy the user's needs and preferences. There are more specified applications that are focused solely on vegan-friendly recommendations, such as Happycow (2024), which, however, does not have much user traffic as the application is specifically vegan. Therefore, information can be wrong, not up to date or even just missing. Furthermore, there is a Google search that sometimes shares blog posts with the vegan-friendly restaurant recommendations depending on the city. Furthermore, there is often the possibility to search the online menu of restaurants to determine if anything suitable is available. Overall, the effort of finding a good restaurant is time-consuming and requires a high effort.

With the new possibilities of LLMs with their natural language processing (NLP) and their ability to process unstructured data and give recommendations based on it (Z. Zhao et al., 2024), LLMs open a new possibility of recommending vegan-friendly restaurants based on menus, labeled items and knowledge base of ingredients of menu items. Along with retrieval augmented generation (RAG), as explained by Ren et al. (2023), online menus can be collected and used in the LLM to generate recommendations.

Within the big data sphere, approaches such as Recommender Systems (RS) have been developed to allow users to find information based on their preferences. RS usually follow a recommendation logic that does not allow for a deeper understanding of user inputs. As a result, the accuracy and efficiency of those systems remains challenging, also considering the huge amount of data possibly available for analysis. Because of these challenges, the development of several techniques such as Content Based Filtering (CBF) relies on recommending results that are based on specific content that the user is interested in or has been interested in. Another approach is Collaborative Filtering (CF) (Chen et al. 2018) which is based on the idea to provide a personalized recommendation for a user considering past interactions (such as clicks or purchases) of other similar users, e.g., users with a common shared interest in a particular item. There are basically two main types of memory-based collaborative filtering. The first is user-based collaborative filtering in which this type deals with identifying similar users or interactors with similar inputs or behaviors that later the recommender would recommend similar items to those users have liked or interacted with. The second main type is item-based collaborative filtering, in which this technique merely focuses on the similar items that have been interesting for some users rather than focusing on the user behavior that a certain user has liked or interacted with to recommend a similar item (Chen et al., 2018).

However, due to the extensive data gathered, such techniques were not sufficient as a basis to function as the user would expect, following up on users' behaviors or products that was

not enough to counter the main challenge of having accurate and efficient results based on each user's preference. Recent efforts have established a range of hybrid collaborative algorithms to combine both model-based CF methods and memory-based CF methods (Chen et al., 2018).

Throughout harnessing the power of the large language models (LLMs) to leverage the evolution of the dining experience, this research will explore how LLMs can effectively tap into structured and unstructured data, such as textual descriptions, icons, images, and even videos from restaurant's menus or websites, to accurately identify vegan-friendly dishes, offering a novel creative approach for personalizing the dietary recommendation in the food industry.

1.1. Problem Statement

Veganism has seen a significant rise in popularity among the public, especially over the past 15 years, becoming more mainstream (Radnitz et al., 2015). Due to this growing popularity, more and more restaurants offer vegan options to their customers. Nevertheless, the problem is that it takes a lot of effort to go through online menus to find any suitable options. There are existing applications such as Happy Cow where a community can label restaurants as vegan-friendly (Happy Cow, 2024) or Tripadvisor as a general restaurant information guide (Tripadvisor, 2024), which provide a manual search for restaurants. Asani et al. (2021) have covered a recommender system that is context-aware, considering user preferences, location, time, and feedback, and based on that recommends nearby restaurants that are open and match the user's food preferences. The gap in the research lies in the fact that vegan options are often marked with different icons or text and are therefore difficult to extract from online menus.

Consequently, the goal of this research is to explore several LLMs and their ability to analyze restaurant menus and websites to find vegan food options and recommendations of vegan-friendly restaurants for users.

1.2. Thesis Statement and Research Questions

For our study, we consider the following thesis statement: LLMs can read out data from a restaurant's menu and identify which dishes carry the ingredients of vegan-friendly options based on text, icons, or images, and recommend vegan-friendly restaurants based on this to match the users' preferences.

Accordingly, our main research question is: How can large language models be efficiently used to identify suitable vegan restaurants?

This question is further investigated by the following sub-research questions (RQs):

RQ1: Which is the best LLM for identifying and recommending vegan restaurants?

RQ2: How does a suitable prompt influence an LLM to receive better recommendations for vegan restaurants based on uploaded restaurant menus?

RQ3: How can the suitability of an LLM be measured in regard to giving good vegan-friendly recommendations?

RQ4: How accurately can LLMs distinguish vegan items from non-vegan items and what are the limitations of LLMs in terms of recognizing unstructured data from PDF files with restaurant menu data?

2. Literature Review

To conduct our literature review and find credible scientific sources, we started with information of the literature provided by our supervisor and as well various databases such as Google Scholar, Elsevier, and Swiscovery. Our search parameters were built of specific parameters and combinations of them, such as “Recommender Systems,” “LLM,” “Vegan,” and “Restaurant.” Furthermore, we used different blog websites as there is not much scientific information about vegan restaurant recommendations available. From a methodology viewpoint, we considered factors such as publication date, authorship, and citations during the research process.

The introduction of a recommendation system (RS) using artificial intelligence in which a system analyzes the data using machine learning techniques to learn the behavior of each individual user (Ayemowa et al. 2024). Thus, the RS once learned about each user's preferences can suggest or recommend suitable content based on that. The upside is that each user will have the chance to connect more with the type of content that he or she prefers, the content can vary from food, movies, books, or any type of products of interest, etc. Thus, the main goal of a recommender system is to provide a personalized suggestion that accurately and efficiently matches the user's preferences, making the user experience richer in terms of connecting with their interests (Ayemowa et al., 2024).

Large language models (LLMs) have recently attracted considerable attention in both academic and industrial fields, as discussed by Zhao et al. (2023). Bubeck et al. (2023) have highlighted their impressive performance, with GPT-4 vastly surpassing prior models, coming close to human-level performance. Unlike earlier models, which were designed for specific tasks, today LLMs can address a wide variety of challenges. Their strong performance in both general natural language tasks and specialized areas has led to their growing use by individuals with essential information needs, which adds to the functionalities of a recommender system.

2.1 Possibilities of Modern LLMs

The reason we are digging into the possibilities of using LLMs is due to its ability to analyze data quickly, allowing the users to communicate in natural language while providing responses without the need to wait for long time to have a certain result established. In our case, we saw the opportunity to use LLMs in a way in which any food enthusiast instead of navigating the internet to look for a certain type of food or restaurant, using an LLM such as GPT to look for it instantly and check all the availabilities within a wide range that the user can decide on.

Due to the huge increase in data, the traditional AI approaches had a lot of limitations when it came to dealing with adaptability and performance, which have led to deeper approaches of driving and learning the data. Based on Chen et al. (2018), this new paradigm was established because of the leap forward in the computational resources and the innovative algorithms such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in which the expansion of the AI's capabilities was humongous. Neural networks where inspiration came from how the human brain functions in the form of nodes with interconnected layers operate to provide a reasonable decision or an answer for an inquiry.

In recent years, the emergence of LLMs such as the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) has transformed how humans can interact with the technology because it allows a natural communication between the human and the computer without the need to understand the computer language as in coding for communication and that is how the natural language processing emerged to allow communication to be done in English language for example. A major progress is the reasoning analysis process that unlike traditional AI which solely focused on pattern recognition in the data without the having the ability of further reasoning; such models can understand and execute tasks over a range of different domains, which strongly shows its potential to learn with a similarity of human-like intelligence. Advances toward human reasoning should suggest better results potentially satisfying the human outcomes needed from the system (Desai et al., 2023).

These types of models have the ability to serve the RS through a deep understanding of user preferences, thus creating precise suggestions based on a reliable learning of the data to add a major value by enhancing the outcome of the results.

2.1.1. Combination of RAG with LLMs

As mentioned by Ren et al. (2023), extending the trained knowledge base of LLMs with the help of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) has shown improvements in reducing hallucination in LLMs. This is because RAG can integrate real-time information, capture data and feed it into the LLMs for the generation process. Furthermore, the retrieval augmentation has proven to be a valuable method for improving LLMs' understanding of their knowledge limitations, which enhances their decision-making capabilities.

The idea of using RAG in our case would be related to providing the LLM with a set of specific data considering that each restaurant had a different way of describing their meals, which makes it confusing for the LLM to detect if the result was relevant to the question in place or not. The objective is to have more enhanced decision making in industries such as food and beverage. Empirical studies have demonstrated the efficiency of RAG in aggregating unstructured data in order to improve task performance (Onwujekwe et al, 2020).

The main goal of using the RAG approach is to counter the challenges that are usually showing up with LLMs when they are used to harness external information sources that could be overwhelming or have many ambiguities. The usage of RAG can enhance the complexity of problem-solving and the degree of accuracy concerning the desired outcomes

or results. There are two main components of a RAG system, the retriever, which is responsible for retrieving information from external sources and then feeding it into the second component, which is called the generator, such as GPT 3 or 4, which takes the information provided by the retriever and then gives a coherent response as a result (Jin et al., 2024). The simple way that RAG functions is the ability to have a combined pipeline of a retriever and generator. It has the benefit of avoiding factual inaccuracies or, in other words, hallucinations of LLM (Jin et al., 2024).

As demonstrated by Liu et al. (2024), RAG can leverage the reasoning ability of LLMs but is also limited due to several factors. One of which is when the data corpus does not include information that is sufficiently specific for the current purpose. For example, if we look into a set of frequently asked questions or summaries, the data may not provide intricate details that would be required for a specific industry; it has shown that RAG capability is limited and cannot provide rich results or could even be simplistic and rather irrelevant. Merrill and Sabharwal (2023) have shown that the power of RAG underlies a constraint of limited reasoning due to the given architecture and the dataset used for training.

There is a clear distinction that was implied by Liu et al. (2024) that it is essential to understand that the process of analyzing a certain document had to be followed up by a certain depth of reasoning. Thus, the information that has been found has to be analyzed within the scope of the user inquiry to make sure it is sufficiently reasonable for the user's needs. Extracting information simply pulls out relevant data or facts from a source in a mechanical approach that does not require much interpretation or reasoning. In contrast, addressing an inquiry is a thoughtful approach that requires a more directional inferential approach to characterize the basis of evidence or reasoning behind an inquiry (Liu et al., 2024).

Based on reality scenarios of applying RAG, it was clear to Liu et al. (2024) that noise in the form of irrelevant data in retrieved documents was the reason for the limited capacity of retrievers due to not having a corpus of data that carries different kinds of information. They also concluded that because of the presence of noisy information processing or information, a further analysis of reasoning was needed as they realized that inaccuracy within the information was interpreted as actually relevant or significant. The RAG objective is to increase the overall performance of the LLMs, but when faced with shallow data, it just gives a simplistic response that does not clearly enhance the system but rather decreases the overall performance of the results.

Moreover, the fast advancement in the recent technology, specifically with the language modeling capabilities are enhancing the accessibility of information which allows the users to feel more convenient while using the technology to enhance their lives in terms of effectiveness of information quality and time. The main challenge when handling big data is an information overload, which leads to a situation where users often do not get the results that they are looking for (Chen et al., 2018).

2.2. Using LLMs for Recommendations

In short, modern RS gather historical knowledge and information about the subject of interest and start their learning process to understand and get to know the likes and preferences of the user. As discussed by Kugler (2024), once the information or knowledge gathering process is completed, it is followed by the process of formulating an algorithm for suggestions that correlate with individual user information.

Solutions using more advanced methods that are being developed currently, such as the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), could offer a big potential for such a niche sector as vegan option recommendations to capture more relative and personalized content. The study conducted by Zhong et al. (2024) suggests that GAN has the strength to recognize and process image information while eliminating any noise accompanying the image in a sense non-relevant content.

The applications of a RS can serve in a wide variety of sectors such as cross-domain RS that allows the transfer of knowledge from related domains, which may also eliminate the need of the single platform suggestions (Liu et al., 2024).

For instance, in the case of UberEATS, instead of suggesting restaurants based on orders, a set of questions can be formulated to gather information about each user when they are creating their own profile on the application. This can be used as a history of the user, which can be combined with orders that have been placed or restaurants that have been checked out by the user. As a result, the recommender system can perform better by providing more accurate results for every user.

In addition, within the gastronomy sector, applications such as UberEATS use RS to enhance their user's experience regarding their interest in a specific type of food or restaurant, allowing its users to have ongoing contact with the application based on their previous orders, geographical location, and their preference of a specific type of cuisine. However, due to the diversity of the food industry, the main methods or approaches that are being used to serve the RS are content-based filtering and machine learning techniques to allow a non-personalized experience of suggestions (Ayemowa et al., 2024).

2.3. Research Gap

Most literature found was precisely focused on providing information or knowledge related to a recommender system (RS), which often considers general knowledge for domains such as e-commerce and social media; however, it also shows a clear gap regarding specific areas, such as vegan restaurant recommendations. Although traditional conventional RS techniques offer personalized suggestions for any kind of product or a type of movie or music, there is limited research that focuses on vegan restaurant recommendations. There are some non-scholar sources, such as websites of recommendation, such as TripAdvisor or HappyCow, that offer such insights; however, they lack accuracy, and they only rely on the users' inputs within those websites. Therefore, there is a need for research that specifically

targets vegan-friendly dining recommendations while operating under a robust methodology that ensures the reliability of relevant suggestions in that specific domain.

Certainly, cross-domain recommendation is gaining strong traction, especially when it is combined with applications of music, video, or even e-learning. The recommendation system has yet to explore other niche areas, such as vegan dining options. In the gastronomy sector, recommending systems approaches are underdeveloped compared to other domains with more mature algorithms, such as in the e-commerce domain. Investigating vegan options using LLMs appears less sophisticated, but the relevance of the available information must be improved so that these models can provide more accurate results. For instance, UberEATS can take the history of orders and combine that with health-related issues and then provide a recommendation of restaurants based on that. This does not necessarily mean that the user actually likes that type of restaurant, possibly they had a friend or a colleague that had a specific dietary option and based on that an order was placed. The vegan specialized insights can be tailored in a way that allows the suggestion to consider information from other users, which may enhance the overall performance of the system, particularly for specialized domains or areas.

It is worth mentioning that there are opportunities for advanced machine learning techniques in the vegan dining recommender system; however, that is yet an area still underexplored. The idea is that the sector is currently relying on basic CF techniques or even non-personalized machine learning approaches, and that is why the results are not very satisfactory for the users.

3. Research Design

In this section, the basic design of our research is presented, including the used data and methods for gathering information to answer our research questions.

3.1. Research Method

This research utilizes the Design Science Research (DSR) approach by Hevner & Chatterjee (2010) as the foundation for evaluating LLMs in their ability to identify and recommend vegan-friendly dining options based on restaurant menu data. DSR is a methodological framework that aims to develop and evaluate the artifacts designed to address identified problems within a specific domain, emphasizing practical relevance and rigorous evaluation. The DSR approach involves iterative phases of design, evaluation, and refinement, ensuring that the research produces useful, validated, and theoretically informed results. The methodology of this research follows the core phases of the DSR framework, which includes the following:

Awareness of Problem: The first phase involves identifying the challenges faced by users when trying to locate vegan-friendly dining options using existing recommender systems or LLMs. This phase aims to clearly define the need for improved LLM capabilities in accurately recognizing and recommending vegan items, particularly given the complex and varied nature of restaurant menus.

Suggestion: Based on our discussion in Section 2.3, the objectives for a suitable solution were established. In this study, the objectives include finding the best LLM for accurately identifying vegan items, understanding effective prompt structures to improve recommendation quality, and exploring the limitations of LLMs in understanding unstructured menu data in PDF formats.

Development: The next phase is the development and adaptation of artifacts, which in this case are LLMs that will be used for the identification and recommendation tasks. This phase involves selecting appropriate LLMs and developing an experimental setup that allows for the comparison of these models in a controlled manner and simulating real-world user interactions.

Evaluation: The effectiveness of the developed artifacts is assessed against the objectives. This phase involves evaluating the LLMs using both quantitative and qualitative metrics, such as accuracy in identifying vegan items, relevance of recommendations, and consistency of responses. The analysis provides insights into the models' strengths and weaknesses.

Conclusion: The results from the evaluation are assessed, highlighting key findings and contributions. Open questions regarding the limitations of LLMs in reading out menu data from PDF files and giving suggestions to the users are addressed, along with plans for further development, such as refining the experimental setup or exploring alternative approaches to enhance LLM performance.

By incorporating the DSR framework, this research not only aims to evaluate LLMs for vegan-friendly restaurant recommendations but also to iteratively refine the process, making practical contributions that could enhance future recommender systems. The goal is to benchmark different LLMs and identify which model, when used with appropriate prompts, is most effective for recommending vegan dining options.

3.2. Data Collection

The data collection process was designed to collect a dataset of menu PDFs from a selection of vegan-friendly and non-vegan-friendly restaurants. This dataset will enable us to assess the ability of LLMs to accurately identify and classify vegan items (addressing RQ1) and to explore the limitations of handling unstructured menu data (addressing RQ4). By sourcing menu files from 20 restaurants with the criteria of the menu being able to download as a PDF file and being in German language and located in Switzerland, we will ensure a diverse range of menu styles, item descriptions, and dietary categorizations, which will challenge the LLMs' ability to interpret and classify vegan items.

A mix of restaurants is chosen to include both vegan-focused establishments and those that are not, with equal representation of vegan-friendly and general dining options. This balance ensures that the experiment can reveal the extent to which each model can accurately identify vegan options even in non-vegan establishments. By including a range of restaurants with different levels of vegan options, from fully vegan to those with few or no vegan items, we will test the models' capacity to navigate the complexities of mixed menus and

ambiguous item descriptions. This will also help in identifying the specific challenges LLMs face when dealing with complex unstructured data, further addressing RQ3. Furthermore, a mix of different labeling techniques from icons to outwritten labeling, such as "(vegan)" or short forms of it like "v+" will be considered.

3.3. Used Techniques

The landscape of tools based on LLMs has expanded significantly and is changing almost every day, offering many options for deployment and experimentation. We have decided to outline a few tools discussed by Vardhan (2024), and we choose to only consider the rather new and up-to-date models by each company:

1. GPT-4 by OpenAI: It is known for its advanced capabilities in understanding context and generating coherent responses, making it well-suited for recommendation tasks (ChatGPT, n.d.).
2. Gemini 1.0 by Google: It emphasizes multilingual capabilities and handles complex queries, making it ideal for nuanced recommendation scenarios (Gemini, n.d.).
3. Claude by Anthropic: Focuses on user-centric, safe responses, minimizing harmful or biased outputs (Claude, n.d.).
4. LLaMA by Meta: An open-source model emphasizing transparency, allowing researchers to experiment and customize freely (Llama 3.2, n.d.).

For this experiment, we selected ChatGPT-4 and Gemini 1.0 mainly due to their easy access to create the experimental setup and their ability to retrieve information from PDF documents. In addition, these tools are able to understand the German language with GPT4 being only around 3% less accurate for German usage than for English according to Achiam et al. (2023). Similar differences were shown for Gemini as in an experiment that the difference to English regarding accuracy was 3% less accurate (Wiik, 2024). These tools will be evaluated on their ability to identify vegan options and generate quality recommendations, highlighting their respective strengths and weaknesses.

3.4. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup involves several sequential steps to simulate a real-world scenario in which a user queries a recommendation system based on restaurant menus. This setup is aimed at addressing RQ1, RQ2, and RQ4 by comparing LLM performance, refining prompt structures, and testing the limitations of understanding menu content. In the first step, each LLM will process the menu PDF files to generate an understanding of the available menu items, which corresponds to RQ4. This step is essential for the LLM to build context and recognize patterns related to vegan items within each menu. The accuracy of identifying vegan options based on the PDF input files will be compared to the manual extraction of the menu items.

Next, a series of user queries (prompts) will be designed to simulate the type of questions a vegan diner might ask, such as "Which vegan dishes are available at this restaurant?" or "I am looking for a vegan restaurant with a burger option." Each prompt is designed to test

different aspects of the LLM functionality, including menu comprehension, dietary restriction identification, and sensitivity to user preferences. This stage of prompt engineering will address RQ2 as it explores the impact of the prompt structure on the quality of LLM recommendations. Furthermore, we create several underlying prompts to give instructions to the LLM and compare how the user prompts are answered.

After prompting, the LLM responses will be recorded and logged for analysis. We will then repeat the experiment with variations in prompt phrasing in a new chat, detail level, and specificity to examine the models' adaptability and consistency in response generation. By systematically adjusting prompts and documenting each response, we can observe patterns and determine which prompt structures yield the most accurate and relevant recommendations for vegan dining.

To evaluate the responses, we will use a combination of quantitative and qualitative metrics that align with the research questions. Specifically, we will consider metrics such as accuracy, relevance, precision, and recall, which will enhance the results of the recommender system, directly addressing RQ4. In line with RQ1, accuracy will be a key metric, as it measures the LLM's ability to correctly identify and recommend vegan items by comparing the model's outputs with ground truth labels derived from our annotated menu data, with answers directly compared with the restaurant information. Relevance will assess how well each recommendation aligns with user preferences, including specific dietary restrictions or ingredient preferences, directly addressing RQ2 by providing insight into how well-structured prompts can guide LLMs toward appropriate recommendations. Precision and recall metrics will also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of the recommender system and ensure that the metrics chosen contributes to enhancing the system's performance, supporting RQ4.

3.5. Prompt Engineering for ChatGPT

To fully harness the power of LLMs, an art of prompt engineering was crafted as a path for ChatGPT to guide it through generating a desired response. Creating the prompt has a high importance factor in determining the maximum efficiency of the LLMs. As suggested by Ekin (2024), the opportunity to craft a suitable engineered prompt may significantly increase the quality of ChatGPT's output. Conversely, a poorly created prompt can generate unreliable and vague results.

As explained by Ekin (2023), prompt engineering is the process of creating a pathway that is more refined for optimizing the ChatGPT output to be explicitly communicated with the user inquiry. Moreover, this practice is currently more of an art than a science because it is like the blueprint of an architect, it defines the structure of the design guiding the model through building precise and accurate responses. For instance, by explicitly specifying the required results, the results of ChatGPT can be enhanced.

It is worth mentioning that there must be some sort of anticipation of how the model will react to a certain input. Thus, because there are several factors affecting the generation and

understanding of the model, such as the training data type and quality, and biases (Ekin, 2023).

3.5.1. Factors Affecting Prompt Selection

There are various factors that influence the prompt specification:

- User intent: to understand what the user goal is for having an inquiry, whether it is an information retrieval, problem solving, or to generate a content; all these aspects play an important role in choosing a prompt (Ekin, 2023).
- Model understanding: to familiarize oneself with the limitations of the model for a certain inquiry while only focusing on the strong parts of the model and rather parting away from its weaknesses (Ekin, 2023).
- Domain specificity: considering the usage of vocabulary that only matches the domain selected to mitigate the risk that the model looking into other domains that probably have different terminologies or vocabularies (Ekin, 2023).
- Clarity and specificity: make sure to support the model with clear instructions and explicit questions to avoid any kind of ambiguity that often is the main cause for unsatisfactory results.
- Constraints: Ensuring that there is a limitation that might be needed to perform effectively by setting a constraint that can be in a shape of specific length or format type (Ekin, 2023).

As suggested by Ekin (2023), all the previous factors are the elements that shape the guideline for the model to effectively give out the desired response. However, that will take several experiments while gathering results and then tweaking the prompt up until the desired responses are generated, which is relevant to our prompt creation to only look for vegan option and not vegetarian.

As a quick example for our research, the user intent would be finding only vegan restaurants or dishes. The model understands vegetarian and vegan as the same when vegetarian is only a dish that does not contain meat and vegan is avoiding any food that comes from an animal. In short, we will consider these factors for the selection of the suitable prompt.

3.5.2. Techniques Affecting Prompt Selection

Moreover, within the topic of prompt engineering, few techniques have been empirically validated in an experimental setting to optimize the model performance (Ronanki et al., 2024). The techniques are as follows:

- Zero-Shot Prompting: This technique is the basic form of communication as it does not rely on providing any examples for the model but rather a certain sentence in natural language to show an explicit problem to be solved or an output that is desired.

- **Few-Shot Prompting:** This technique relies as a follow-up on zero-shot prompting as it sets a condition at the inference time once a non-accurate result from the zero-shot prompting occurs; In other words, tweaking the prompt furthermore.
- **Chain of Thought Prompting:** This technique relies on guiding the model to create a coherent response based on a series of intermediate reasoning steps that leads to the desired output. It was observed by Ronanki et al. (2024) that this technique can enhance the reasoning capabilities as it helps the model to rely on a set of steps to provide a response.

As mentioned by Ronanki et al. (2024), despite all the efforts and studies for finding out the best prompt patterns for a specific task, no one was found that focused on measuring the ability of the patterns to craft the input prompts. It is worth mentioning that among other patterns, question refinement was seen by Ronanki et al. (2024) as particularly effective regarding consistency and reliability.

Considering our use case, we decided to use zero-shot prompting as it appears suitable from a practical point of view to expect a concrete response to an input question such as “Which of those dishes is a vegan dish?”

4. Artifact Development

For the basic setup of the experiment, we started with a manual classification of restaurant menus including their names into five categories, as described in Table 1. The word “Labels” refers to any form of writing or visual signalization of menu items if they are vegetarian or vegan.

Table 1: Restaurants and categories.

Category	Assigned Restaurants including URL
Completely vegan with no labels (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bakery Bakery, https://www.bakerybakery.ch/_files/ugd/20a5ae_a92756252deb4a2cb8401788f7e2dbae.pdf - Beans & Nuts, https://files.designer.hoststar.ch/1c/dc/1cdc44bf-bb0a-4cf4-b8b4-a01948bd2528.pdf
Mixed with no labels (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Da Nino, https://pizzeriadanino.ch/ - Injera, https://www.injera-restaurant.ch/media/Speisekarte/Speisekarte-2024.pdf
Mixed with labels (9)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brasserie Obstberg, https://brasserie-obstberg.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Speisekarte_Obstberg-November2024bisjanuar2025.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kornhauskeller, https://kornhaus-bern.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Kornhauskeller-Speisekarte-10.24-HW-2.pdf - La Chouette, https://api.kptl.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/LA_CHOUETTE_MENU_DEUTSCH_AUG_2024-2.pdf - Mishio, https://mishio.ch/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Mishio_grundkarte_DE_210x210mm_web_2023-11.pdf - Molino, https://molino.ch/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/molino_speisekarte_kat1_102024_de.pdf - Pitteria, https://www.pittaria.ch/ - Piu, https://www.piu-ristorante.ch/site/assets/files/1032/piu-speisekarte-be-de-07_24.pdf - Santa Lucia, https://www.bindella.ch/wp-content/uploads/Santa-Lucia-Speisekarte-10.24.pdf - Tenz Momos, https://tenz-public-prod.sos-ch-dk-2.exo.io/filer_public/d9/17/d917957a-d3dc-48ac-a5dd-e33da922f8d2/240312_menukarte_bern_digital_de.pdf
<p>Non-vegan with labels (3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brasserie Bellevue, https://www.bellevue-palace.ch/ - Harmonie, https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/649ab3da9027ec9d82010c7e/66fd7ba88fe9954b939406f7_Speisekarte_Harmonie_Herbst_2024_de.pdf - Lötschberg, https://loetschbergbern.ch/angebote/speisekarte/
<p>Non-vegan with no labels (4)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal, https://entrecote.ch/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Federal_Speisekarte_A4_DE_10_2022.pdf - Moules-Edy, https://www.moules-edy.ch/_files/ugd/08042b_047707da2a4c4c248f5c9825d0d705a7.pdf - Mühlirad, https://www.muehlirad-bern.ch/aesse-u-trinke - NOA, https://api2.lunchgate.ch/digital-menu/dm/digital-menu/604c2f5840a0bf3898a40d14257d593e

These data were used as a knowledge base for our experiments. We decided to use the paid version of ChatGPT, Chat GPT4o (ChatGPT, n.d.). For that, we configured the following prompt:

“You are specialized in vegan restaurant recommendations. Analyze information provided in PDFs or described by users, extracting relevant details about only vegan-friendly options while making a clear distinction between vegan and vegetarian with avoiding and excluding vegetarian which is another dietary option that excludes meat, fish, and poultry, however, may include dairy, eggs, and honey. Tailor your responses to vegan options which must exclude all animal-derived products, including but not limited to meat, fish, poultry, dairy, eggs, honey, gelatine, and any derivatives. Identify ambiguities where ingredients are unclear as well as highlight common misconceptions or mislabeled items (e.g., products labeled "vegetarian" but assumed to be vegan), and finally personal preferences. Communicate clearly, avoid assumptions, and confirm details when necessary to ensure accurate and inclusive recommendations. Present your answers in English language always but have the capacity to read files when uploaded whether they are presented in German or English language. Only answer questions based on the knowledge base “Prompt” provided accurately and precisely while ensuring to include recommendations or actions for improving the labeling or offering of vegan-friendly wherever possible.”

Further, we uploaded the 20 PDF documents of different menus as a knowledge base to the GPT so that answers could be retrieved from them. We have disabled the function of Internet search with the background that we use the knowledge base as a simulation of RAG, which could be broadened over many more menus and restaurants but are not considered in our Proof of Concept.

URL to the created LLM solution: <https://chatgpt.com/g/g-674612b1989081919de1280889ab9cea-vegan-dining-gpt>

For the second LLM, we have built a Chat in Poe, a tool where custom built GPTs can be created (Poe, n.d.). We have used the same prompt in the configuration and uploaded the 20 documents. Due to some problems there, three documents could not be uploaded for the restaurants: Da Nino, NOA and Brasserie Obstberg. Poe could not read out these documents and see them as a data input for our created chat. For the LLM, we have chosen Gemini.1.5 Pro as a Version to answer within our created chat.

URL to the created LLM: https://poe.com/Vegan_Dining_GPT

5. Evaluation

In this section, the experimental results will be evaluated and the findings discussed.

5.1. Qualitative Output

In the first experiment, we used our created artifacts to receive information from the LLM and compare how accurate the results were based on the LLM with the given data input, as PDF files without specifying an underlying prompt. Afterwards, we checked the same query with the underlying prompt created in Chapter 4. In the following table, we listed how many dishes were actually vegan, based on manual analysis and compared it to how many dishes the two LLM’s would return with the prompt: “List all the possible menu options per

restaurant which are suitable for me.” In brackets, we will disclose how many answers were wrong out of these total amounts.

Table 2: Number of dishes identified per restaurant of each LLM with a simple prompt.

Category	Restaurants	Number of vegan dishes identified by the authors	Number of vegan dishes identified by ChatGPT4o	Number of vegan dishes identified by Gemini 1.5
Completely vegan with no labels (2)	Bakery Bakery	11	0	0
	Beans & Nuts	15	0	0
Mixed with no labels (2)	Da Nino	3	0	0
	Injera	4	2	0
Mixed with labels (9)	Brasserie Obstberg	1	3 (3)	0
	Kornhauskeller	8	2	0
	La Chouette	20	3	0
	Mishio	7	2	0
	Molino	18	2	0
	Pitteria	4	1	0
	Piu	7	5	0
	Santa Lucia	9	2	0
	Tenz Momos	6	3	0
Non-vegan with labels (3)	Brasserie Bellevue	0	0	0
	Harmonie	0	2 (2)	0
	Lötschberg	0	1 (1)	0
Non-vegan with no labels (4)	Federal	0	0	0
	Moules-Edy	0	0	0
	Mühlirad	0	0	0
	NOA	0	0	0

With the same prompt, Gemini 1.5 could not return any valid information as everything was hallucinated by it. In contrast, GPT4o could identify at least some vegan options that were correct.

For the second experiment, we opened a new chat and put the underlying prompt defined in Chapter 4 into the LLM, thus trying to optimize the results.

Table 3: Number of dishes identified per restaurant of each LLM with an optimized prompt.

Category	Restaurants	Number of vegan dishes identified by the authors	Number of vegan dishes identified by ChatGPT4o	Number of vegan dishes identified by Gemini 1.5
Completely Vegan with no Labels (2)	Bakery Bakery	11	0	0
	Beans & Nuts	15	3	0
Mixed with no Labels (2)	Da Nino	3	0	0
	Injera	4	3	1
Mixed with Labels (9)	Brasserie Obstberg	1	0	0
	Kornhauskeller	8	3	7
	La Chouette	20	2	0
	Mishio	7	3	0
	Molino	18	0	0
	Pizzeria	4	2	0
	Piu	7	4	0
	Santa Lucia	9	2	0
	Tenz Momos	6	4	0
Non-Vegan with Labels (3)	Brasserie Bellevue	0	0	0
	Harmonie	0	0	0
	Lötschberg	0	0	0
Non-Vegan with no Labels (4)	Federal	0	0	0
	Moules-Edy	0	0	0
	Mühlirad	0	0	0
	NOA	0	0	0

Based on this comparison, we see the following results to answer our research questions RQ1, RQ2, and RQ4. Regarding the quality of the answers, the results are quite obvious. GPT4o has delivered many more results based on the given dataset while Gemini 1.5 was struggling both with and without prompting. Therefore, in this test we can answer for RQ1 that GPT4o was much better in returning good menu options per restaurant.

Regarding RQ4, the ability to read out PDF documents and give information based on them about vegan dishes was rather disappointing. What is clearly visible is that both LLMs do not understand the context of a whole menu and can therefore identify completely vegan restaurants. However, there are also difficulties with recognizing menu options that are not clearly labeled as vegan, and one would have to assume from the name or ingredients list if it is vegan or not. What was interesting is that if asked more specifically for one restaurant, GPT4o could return more results. As with the prompt: "List all vegan options for La Chouette," it would return 8 options doing already much better than in the tests above where 3 or 2 were returned. However, Gemini 1.5 would return with the same prompt, that there are no vegan dishes for La Chouette, specifying that menu items are marked with a (v) as vegetarian but not with a (v+) as vegan. It shows that the pdf document was not understood completely. With a further prompt: "Out of all your knowledge data, search and return all labels that label menu items as vegan.," we tried to understand how well the labels actually were understood and recognized by the LLMs to see if that is the reason for its weak returns. They both understood that (v+) is the most commonly used labeling of vegan options and both also recognized vegan options where the text "vegan" occurs but without a respective label. What seemed to cause problems for both was that some restaurants used just a (v), and this was not clear for them. What both LLMs completely missed were all labels based on icons, where on the menu there was a picture of a leaf for example, which is also often used. From our findings, we can say that neither LLM did well in returning the unstructured data from PDF documents nor could it recognize most of the menu options and list them all. However, it was good that usually wrong answers in the sense of identifying non-vegan dishes as vegan are missing, especially after prompting. This shows that both could clearly identify vegan options as vegan if this was a sure answer; however, they missed a lot of possible other answers.

Regarding RQ2 about how a prompt can make the results better, this gives us no clear answer based on our experiment. As discussed in the literature review, good prompts can significantly create better answers from an LLM. What we could observe with our prompt is that the LLM got better in recognizing vegan options which were not labeled, and it could reduce the number of wrong answers from 6 to 0 and for Gemini 1.5 we got at least 7 menu options from 2 restaurants compared to 0 beforehand. However, for GPT4o it would reduce for some restaurants the number of dishes it returned, therefore providing us with overall fewer identified dishes which are vegan than beforehand but with also no more erroneous responses. Therefore, we concluded that, in our case, the prompt was creating better responses but reduced the number of overall menu items slightly.

5.2. Survey Analysis

We created a survey to measure the effectiveness of LLMs in terms of their responses based on the user's inputs. The survey was undertaken by six participants aged from 21 to 42, including three females and three males. They all used and tested the two LLMs themselves without further instructions and answered the survey afterwards. The introduction of the survey was as follows: "Vegan-friendly restaurants have seen a significant surge in demand, and recommendation systems provide a means for users to navigate the vast number of restaurant choices available to them. In recent years, large language models have demonstrated promising results in addressing sensitive and ethical concerns in NLP tasks, such as misinformation. Whether these models can demonstrate efficacy for domains targeting sensitive and ethical concerns, such as vegan-friendly restaurant recommendations, remains unexplored. Given the notable drawbacks and ethical challenges associated with the commercialization of veganism, this experiment empirically explores the ability of large language models to provide accurate, sensitive, and balanced vegan-friendly restaurant recommendations. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to study how large language models perform for vegan-friendly restaurant recommendations and the first to provide insight into the integrity of the results returned. We ask you kindly to try out using this setup of advanced LLMs like ChatGPT-4 and Gemini 1.0, which is configured with specific prompts and a curated knowledge base of restaurant menus. Later, please answer the following questions based on how your experience was?"

The questions and answering options were created for both ChatGPT and Gemini as follows:

1. How accurately did the LLM of your choice identify vegan dishes from the menus?
 - 1) Very accurate
 - 2) Somewhat accurate
 - 3) Fair
 - 4) Not accurate
2. Were the recommendations aligned with your preferences and dietary restrictions?
 - 1) Highly relevant
 - 2) Fairly relevant
 - 3) Not relevant at all
3. Did the responses clearly differentiate between vegan and vegetarian options?
 - 1) Very clear
 - 2) Clear
 - 3) Not clear
4. How easy was it to interact with the system and input your queries?
 - 1) Very easy
 - 2) Fairly easy
 - 3) Difficult

5. Were there any ambiguities or misinterpretations in the system's responses? If yes, please describe.
 - 1) No ambiguities
 - 2) Minor ambiguities
 - 3) Major ambiguities
6. How satisfied are you with the system's performance in identifying and recommending vegan options?
 - 1) Very satisfied
 - 2) Fairly satisfied
 - 3) Not satisfied
7. What features or improvements would you suggest making the system more effective? Please provide briefly in a few lines based on your experience what would be your suggestion?

(Free text answer.)

The survey setting was established in a set of questions and each question considered a certain criterion that the user would reflect upon on how they perceived the outcome. The criteria of the survey were as follows:

1. Accuracy of LLM to identify vegan dishes from menus.
2. The recommendations of LLM relevancy with dietary restrictions.
3. Whether responses showed a clear distinction between vegan and vegetarian.
4. The friendliness of the interaction between the system and the user
5. Whether the LLM responses carried any kind of ambiguities or misinterpretations.
6. The satisfaction level of the user with regards to the LLM's responses.
7. Finally, suggestions by users on the possibilities of improvement.

To assess the criteria in detail, each question is linked to a specific evaluation criterion as follows:

1. Gather user scores for measuring precision (percentage of true vegan items correctly identified out of all identified items) and recall (percentage of true vegan items identified out of all vegan items present).
2. Score the responses based on user feedback regarding alignment with the stated preferences.
3. Evaluate textual outputs for linguistic clarity and use of consistent terminology (e.g., use of "vegan" vs. "vegetarian"), as well as analyzing user comments on confusion or misinterpretation.
4. Gather user ratings on ease of use in terms of reformulated queries needed to achieve the desired output.
5. Review cases where users expressed dissatisfaction or confusion with the output and compare results from several LLMs to pinpoint performance gaps.
6. Categorize and rank user suggestions by frequency and relevance while integrating findings into an iterative refinement process.

7. Compute overall satisfaction scores based on user ratings and analyze qualitative feedback to understand broader user sentiments.

Based on each criterion mentioned above, we have received the following feedback link to the survey details:

1. Accuracy

- ChatGPT:
 - Rated "Very Accurate" by 16.67% of respondents and "Somehow Accurate" by 83.33%.
 - No respondents rated it as "Less Accurate" or "Not Accurate."
 - Implication: ChatGPT showed a high degree of accuracy in identifying vegan dishes although there is room for improvement in precision.
- Gemini:
 - Only 33.33% of respondents rated it as "Somehow Accurate," while 66.67% rated it as "Less Accurate."
 - No "Very Accurate" ratings were given.
 - Implication: Gemini struggled with accuracy, significantly underperforming compared to ChatGPT.

2. Relevancy

- ChatGPT:
 - Achieved 100% "Very Relevant" ratings, indicating strong alignment with user preferences and dietary needs.
 - Implication: ChatGPT effectively tailors its recommendations to individual requirements.
- Gemini:
 - 66.67% rated it as "Somehow Relevant," while the others rated it "Less Relevant" (16.67%) or "Not Relevant" (16.67%).
 - Implication: Gemini displayed notable gaps in aligning recommendations with user needs.

3. Distinction

- ChatGPT:
 - Rated "Very Clear" by 33.33% and "Somehow Clear" by 66.67%.
 - Implication: ChatGPT demonstrates moderate success in distinguishing between vegan and vegetarian options but could benefit from more explicit categorizations.

- Gemini:
 - Only 33.33% rated it as "Somehow Clear," while 50% found it "Less Clear," and 16.67% found it "Not Clear."
 - Implication: Gemini responses often caused confusion regarding dietary distinctions.

4. Ease of Interaction

- ChatGPT:
 - Rated "Very Easy" to interact with by 83.33%, with the remaining 16.67% rating it "Somehow Easy."
 - Implication: ChatGPT provides an intuitive and user-friendly interface for queries.
- Gemini:
 - Only 33.33% found it "Very Easy," while 50% rated it "Somehow Easy," and 16.67% rated it "Less Easy."
 - Implication: Gemini's interface may require refinements to improve the user experience.

5. Ambiguities

Ambiguities were noted, particularly with Gemini, where it was reported to fabricate responses or recommend dishes with unclear ingredients (e.g., "soup of the day"). ChatGPT, while slightly better, still had limited menu options and occasionally lacked comprehensive coverage.

6. Satisfaction

Most users were more satisfied with using ChatGPT as they felt more comfortable using it. This could also be due to ChatGPT familiarity compared to Gemini. However, regardless of the reason, the satisfaction of using ChatGPT was higher than that of using Gemini as several respondents recorded that their inquiry was not properly matched to what they asked for compared to the same experience when they had used ChatGPT.

7. Suggestions

- Improved detection of vegan dishes without explicit labeling.
- Enhancing the range of restaurant options and incorporating more precise location data.
- Addressing the confusion between vegan and vegetarian definitions.

8. Survey Conclusion

Referring to RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3, the survey results highlight ChatGPT as the superior performer when compared to Gemini, particularly in terms of accuracy, relevance, and usability, although it is not without its limitations. Gemini's performance, on the other hand,

was suboptimal, particularly in accuracy and clarity. For both systems, expanding their database, refining their understanding of dietary nuances, and enhancing clarity in recommendations could significantly improve user satisfaction as suggested by the users on their feedback. The users conducted the survey without any kind of prompt implemented by us. Thus, some of our insights are grounded on a broader range of prompting techniques besides those used in our previous experiments. This shows, in particular, that prompting does make a difference in LLM usage for the given use case.

Table 4-Survey Results GPT vs. Gemini (based on the most frequent answer)

Criteria	ChatGPT	Gemini
Accuracy	Very accurate	Somehow accurate
Relevancy	Very relevant	Somehow relevant
Distinction	Very clear	Somehow clear
Interaction	Mostly easy	Somehow easy to less easy
Ambiguity	Minor ambiguity	Major ambiguity
Satisfaction	Fairly satisfied	Less satisfied

6. Conclusions

Our research was based on investigating how large language models such as ChatGPT 4.0 and Gemini 1.5 could act as enablers for improving vegan dining experiences in Switzerland using unstructured menu data from different restaurants. The study itself focused on whether LLMs could correctly identify some vegan-friendly options while recognizing their roles in improving user experiences in that particular niche domain. They were able to provide partially satisfactory results in response to the inquiries in the sense that options identified as vegetarian were usually correct, while non-vegetarian options were frequently not identified as such. Our motivation to explore this field stems from a personal experience we encountered while searching for vegan menu options in restaurants. From that, we know that the manual search for vegan-friendly menus may require quite some effort.

Our key findings are that ChatGPT-4 and Gemini 1.5 perform differently, with ChatGPT-4 outperforming Gemini 1.5 in accuracy, relevance, and user satisfaction. Both models have limitations, particularly in recognizing icon-based labeling or vague menu entries. ChatGPT-4

has been shown to be more responsive in prompt engineering, with greater clarity and relevance of output, making the output satisfactory for users.

Moreover, another parameter we explored is the impact of prompt engineering techniques by using structured prompts, which can direct the LLMs to generate more defined outputs. Indeed, we found that the effectiveness of LLMs significantly improved the accuracy of differentiating between vegan and vegetarian options, as well as an increase in the results of identifying vegan dishes. In our test scenario, it had only a little effect because the overall results provided by LLMs are still far from matching the number of vegan dishes declared by restaurants.

Additionally, we investigated how both LLMs found it difficult to understand different datasets, which might be in another language or have different names for dishes. We also found that both LLMs struggled with icon-based labels and unstructured menu presentation formats, suggesting that LLM capabilities are still bound by the quality of data and presentation, as well as a pre-set of data that should be implemented beforehand.

Furthermore, the dependence on a manually designed dataset restricts its real-life implementation and scaling. The latter focuses on menu annotations, exposing deficiencies in addressing multicultural and multilingual aspects. The competitive implications of these findings can also be important for practical reasons, such as enabling LLMs to be integrated into applications for real-world use cases, particularly for consumers who would like customized dining recommendations. Therefore, businesses can help optimize their menu design in terms of readability and user experience to reach a wider audience.

Future studies should emphasize the generation of robust, diverse datasets where data encodings include different languages, various icon-based annotations, and patterns of menus. This would improve the training and evaluation of LLMs. We also see the importance of merging LLMs more with RAG systems; the challenge of real-time information retrieval is likely to be mitigated, allowing for synchronized updates and accurate responses, which should also eliminate the problem of having pre-loaded data sets. Moreover, the fast pace of novel LLMs being developed requires continuous effort to repeat the investigation of their capabilities.

We also recommend the importance of retrieving data in real-time and applying feedback from users, which will ensure concrete, yet adaptive learning opportunities and justify a constant feedback mechanism where the recommendation engine consistently improves.

In summary, the study stresses the importance of LLMs in expert-based recommendation systems and the specific area of vegan restaurant content. This highlight makes it critical that we continue working on improving the ability of LLMs to provide very accurate, user-centered suggestions by addressing the challenges we have framed here and expanding future research pathways. We hope that it will provide seamless user experiences in a wide array of niche domains while also addressing access and personalization gaps.

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